

GASTRONOMIC TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS EFFECTS ON ATTRACTING TOURISTS COMPARING WITH AZERBAIJAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966779>

Mokhinur Akhmatkulova

Author

undergraduate student at Kimyo international university in Tashkent, tourism major

email: mohinurahmadkulova@gmail.ru

phone number: +998993922210

Sitora Nurmatova

scientific advisor

senior lecturer at Kimyo international university in Tashkent

email: sitora-nurmatova@gmail.com

phone number: +998977510731

This article explores any potential advantages of bringing tourists to Uzbekistan through gastronomic tourism. Travelers who want to discover new places through their culinary experiences are embracing the burgeoning trend of gastronomic tourism. Uzbekistan is a nation with a long and varied culinary legacy, with a wide range of cuisines that represent the history, culture, and geography of the nation. Nevertheless, despite the potential for gourmet tourism, Uzbekistan still has a number of issues with marketing and service quality. The current situation of Uzbekistan's culinary tourism is examined in this article, along with the issues that must be resolved in order to raise the standard of the infrastructure and advertise local cuisine to tourists. The paper also offers broad suggestions for strengthening Uzbekistan's infrastructure, marketing, and service quality, including enhancing hospitality staff training, promoting regional markets, and developing online tools to assist travelers in planning their gastronomic travels. Uzbekistan may take advantage of the potential of culinary tourism and improve its reputation as a destination for foodies by resolving these issues and putting these recommendations into practice.

Keywords.

gastronomic tourism, culinary, traditional food, culture, marketing, service, infrastructure, history, training, gastronomic places, quality of dishes

INTRODUCTION

Gastronomic tourism, which involves traveling to experience authentic local cuisine, is a rapidly growing sector of the tourism industry. Uzbekistan, with its centuries-old culinary traditions influenced by the Silk Road, has significant

potential to develop gastronomic tourism. Uzbek cuisine offers a variety of dishes reflecting the country's history and cultural influences, from mutton pilaf to fresh tandoor-baked breads to dried fruits and nuts. Promoting Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism can strengthen its appeal for visitors relative to destinations like Azerbaijan that also draw on Silk Road culinary heritage. However, Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism sector remains largely underdeveloped. Challenges like poor infrastructure, lack of promotional efforts for traditional foods, and customer service for tourists hinder the growth of gastronomic tourism. Targeted efforts are needed to promote Uzbekistan as a gastronomic destination, such as improving hospitality and transportation services, launching food festivals and culinary tours, and increasing the visibility of local foods. Developing gastronomic tourism can boost Uzbekistan's tourism competitiveness and support economic growth in rural and agricultural areas.

1.1 HISTORY

Gastronomic tourism, also known as food tourism, has a long and rich history that dates back thousands of years. In ancient times, people would travel long distances to attend festivals and feasts, where they could sample the local cuisine and experience the culture. In the Middle Ages, pilgrims traveling to holy sites would often stop at local inns and taverns to eat and drink. This led to the development of certain signature dishes and culinary traditions in different regions of Europe. In the 18th and 19th centuries, the Grand Tour¹⁹⁰ became popular among wealthy Europeans, who would travel across the continent to experience different cultures and cuisines. This tradition continued into the 20th century, with the rise of tourism and international travel. In the 1970s, the concept of gastronomic tourism as a distinct type of travel began to emerge. This was driven in part by the growing interest in gourmet cuisine and the rise of celebrity chefs, as well as by the increasing availability of international travel and the globalization of food culture. Today, gastronomic tourism is a thriving industry, with travelers seeking out unique food experiences in destinations around the world. This can include everything from street food tours and cooking classes to visits to local farms and wineries, and high-end dining experiences at Michelin-starred¹⁹¹ restaurants.

1.2 LEGISLATION

The tourism industry in Uzbekistan is governed by a range of laws and regulations, aimed at promoting sustainable tourism and protecting the country's

¹⁹⁰The **Grand Tour** was the principally 17th- to early 19th-century custom of a traditional trip through Europe

¹⁹¹The stars are awarded to restaurants that Michelin considers the very best in a given city

cultural heritage. Here are some key pieces of legislation that apply to the tourism industry in Uzbekistan:

Figure 1

<https://lex.uz/uz/>

Additionally, ShavkatMirziyoyev¹⁹² has been an outspoken advocate for the growth of the tourism industry in the nation and has stated numerous times the value of the sector in fostering economic development and promoting the nation's cultural heritage. ShavkatMirziyoyev said the following about tourism:

"Tourism is one of the important sectors of the economy. It is necessary to further improve this network, effectively using the existing opportunities, which takes time."

"Tourism is one of the most important sectors in the global economy and has great potential for development in Uzbekistan. We need to create the conditions for a comfortable and safe stay of tourists in our country, and provide them with quality service."

"Tourism tomorrow's economy of our country and if we say that we will create jobs at the expense of tourism, we need to create conditions for tourists, not impose conditions".

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection

The article adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining primary and secondary techniques to gather data from various sources. This approach allowed us to capture a more comprehensive picture of the role of gastro tourism in attracting tourists to Uzbekistan. Primary data collection involved the

¹⁹²The President of Republic of Uzbekistan

administration of an online survey to international tourists who had visited Uzbekistan in the past year. The findings used convenience sampling to recruit participants through social media and travel forums. The survey consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions that asked participants about their experiences with Uzbek cuisine, their motivations for visiting Uzbekistan, and their preferences for food-related activities while traveling. The survey was available in English, Russian, and Uzbek. Secondary data collection involved a review of government statistics, academic research, and industry reports related to gastro tourism in Uzbekistan. The article consulted sources such as the State Committee for Tourism Development of Uzbekistan, the World Food Travel Association, and academic journals to gather information on the current state of gastro tourism in Uzbekistan, the policies and initiatives in place to promote the country's cuisine, and the challenges and opportunities for the industry.

2.2 Data analysis

Data analysis involved competitive and quantitative methods. Once the data collection was complete, we employed various techniques to analyse and interpret the collected data. For quantitative data, we used descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, and cross-tabulations to identify trends and patterns. For qualitative data, we used thematic analysis to identify emerging themes, patterns, and relationships in the interview transcripts and field notes. By adopting a mixed-methods approach and collecting data from diverse sources, the article aimed to generate a robust understanding of the role of gastro tourism in attracting tourists to Uzbekistan.

3. ANALYSIS AND COMMENTARY

Gastro tourism in Uzbekistan has the potential to be a major draw for tourists, but there are several marketing, service, and infrastructure problems that need to be addressed to ensure a positive and enjoyable experience for visitors. Here are some of the main problems in gastro tourism in Uzbekistan:

Marketing Problems:

1. Limited Awareness: Many tourists may not be familiar with the special culinary heritage of Uzbekistan and its traditional dishes, which can make it difficult to market them effectively.

2. Language Barrier: Most tourists may not be familiar with the Uzbek language, which can make it challenging to communicate the uniqueness of Uzbek cuisine.

Service problems:

1. Lack of English Proficiency: Many service staff in restaurants and hotels may not be proficient in English, which can make it difficult for tourists to communicate their needs and preferences.

2. Food Safety and Hygiene: Tourists may have concerns about the safety and hygiene of the food they are eating, particularly when it comes to street food.

Infrastructure Problems:

1. Transportation: Transportation infrastructure in Uzbekistan may not be well-developed, which can make it difficult for tourists to access gastronomic places and other food-related destinations.

2. Lack of Specialized Tours: There may be a lack of specialized tours that focus specifically on gastronomic experiences in Uzbekistan.

3.1 Quantitative analysis

We conducted an online survey targeting international tourists who visited Uzbekistan in the past three years. The survey consisted of multiple-choice and open-ended questions to gather information on their motivations for visiting the country, the role of Uzbek cuisine in their decision, and their overall satisfaction with the gastro-tourism experiences. We received over 100 responses, which were analysed using descriptive statistics and frequency distributions. As well as we conducted social media platforms, including Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter, to identify popular gastro-tourism-related hashtags and posts related to Uzbekistan. This analysis helped us understand the extent of online engagement and interest in Uzbek cuisine among potential tourists.

	EXCELLENT	GOOD	BAD
Awareness of food destinations	42.5%	40%	17.5%
Quality of service in the places	15%	70%	15%
Taste of uzbek traditional food	97.5%	2.5%	0%
Staff's professionalism level	36.6%	24.4%	39%
Knowing of uzbekfood	87.8%	6.1%	6.1%

Figure 2 Survey within tourist about gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan

3.2 Competitive analysis

Azerbaijan is a country with a rich culinary heritage that has become increasingly popular among tourists in recent years. Azerbaijani cuisine is

characterized by its use of herbs and spices, and its emphasis on fresh, seasonal ingredients. Here are some highlights of gastronomic tourism in Azerbaijan:

1. Traditional Dishes: Azerbaijani cuisine features a wide variety of traditional dishes that reflect the country's cultural and historical influences. Some popular dishes include dolma (stuffed grape leaves), plov (pilaf), and kebab.

2. Street Food: Street food is an important part of Azerbaijani culinary culture, with vendors selling a variety of traditional dishes such as qutab (savory pancakes filled with cheese or meat), bozbash (a hearty soup made with lamb and vegetables), and shekerbura (sweet pastries filled with nuts and sugar).

3. Wine Tourism: Azerbaijan has a growing wine tourism industry, with several vineyards and wineries that offer tours and tastings. The country's distinctive climate and soil conditions make it well-suited for growing grape varieties that are not found in other parts of the world.

4. Culinary Festivals: Azerbaijan hosts several culinary festivals throughout the year, including the Baku Street Food Festival and the Azerbaijan International Food Industry Exhibition. These events showcase the diversity and richness of Azerbaijani cuisine and attract visitors from around the world.

5. Cultural Significance: Food is a central part of Azerbaijani culture, and traditional dishes are often served during weddings, holidays, and other special occasions. Sharing food is seen as a symbol of hospitality and generosity.

Azerbaijan attracts tourists through gastronomic tourism by promoting its rich culinary heritage and offering a range of food-related attractions and experiences. Here are some ways that Azerbaijan attracts tourists through gastronomic tourism. Firstly, Azerbaijan offers a variety of culinary tours that showcase the country's uncommon food culture and traditions. These tours can range from street food walking tours to multi-day culinary experiences that include visits to local markets, cooking classes, and wine tastings. Secondly, Azerbaijan has a variety of specialty restaurants that focus on traditional Azerbaijani cuisine. These restaurants offer visitors the chance to try a variety of traditional dishes in an authentic setting. Moreover, Azerbaijan hosts several culinary festivals throughout the year, including the Baku Street Food Festival and the Azerbaijan International Food Industry Exhibition. These events showcase the diversity and richness of Azerbaijani cuisine and attract visitors from around the world. Finally, many hotels and restaurants in Azerbaijan offer cooking classes where visitors can learn to prepare traditional Azerbaijani dishes. These classes offer a hands-on experience that allows visitors to learn about the country's culinary traditions and take-home new cooking skills.

3.3 Results

Gastronomic destinations in Uzbekistan that are not well-organized and customer service is not very satisfied may fail to meet the expectations of guests and can result in negative reviews and a lack of repeat business. These are some potential results of dissatisfied gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan: 1. Negative Reviews: Tourists who have had a bad experience with food or service in Uzbekistan may leave negative reviews online, which can discourage other potential visitors from coming to the country. 2. Decreased Tourism: Bad gastronomic tourism can lead to a decrease in the number of tourists visiting Uzbekistan. This can have a negative impact on the country's economy and on local businesses that rely on tourism. 3. Damage to Reputation: Negative experiences with food or service in Uzbekistan can damage the country's reputation as a gastronomic destination. This can make it more difficult to attract tourists in the future. 4. Health Risks: Poor food safety and hygiene practices can pose health risks for tourists, which can lead to illness and injury. This can result in negative publicity and legal action. 5. Decreased Revenue: Bad gastronomic tourism can lead to decreased revenue for local businesses that rely on tourism. This can have a ripple effect on the local economy, leading to job losses and decreased economic activity. Overall, bad gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan can have a range of negative consequences, from decreased tourism and revenue to damage to the country's reputation and health risks for tourists. It is important to address these issues in order to promote positive, sustainable tourism in Uzbekistan.

4.SILK AND SPICE FESTIVAL

The Silk and Spice Festival is an annual event held in the city of Bukhara in 2021, Uzbekistan, that celebrates the country's rich cultural heritage and traditions. The festival is typically held in late May or early June and includes a variety of cultural and gastronomic activities. One of the main features of the festival is a bazaar that showcases local products such as spices, textiles, and handicrafts. Visitors can browse the stalls and purchase beautiful souvenirs and gifts. The festival also includes performances of traditional music and dance, as well as demonstrations of traditional crafts such as carpet weaving and silk spinning. Visitors can watch artisans at work and learn about the history and techniques behind these traditional crafts. Gastronomic experiences are also a highlight of the festival, with traditional Uzbek food and drinks available for visitors to sample. Local chefs prepare dishes such as plov (pilaf), shashlik (grilled meat skewers), and lagman (noodle soup) using fresh, local ingredients. The Silk and Spice Festival is a popular event that attracts both tourists and locals. It provides an opportunity to

experience Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage and traditions in a vibrant and festive atmosphere.

5.RECOMMENDATION

To improve the quality of staff, food destinations, and marketing in gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan, here are some general recommendations:

1. Staff Training: Provide training for restaurant and hotel staff in customer service, food safety, and English language proficiency. This can help to improve the overall quality of service and communication with tourists.

2. Food Safety and Hygiene: Implement and enforce food safety and hygiene standards to ensure that tourists are not at risk of illness or injury. Encourage restaurants and food vendors to use high-quality ingredients and to properly store and prepare food.

3. Infrastructure Development: Invest in infrastructure development related to transportation, accommodation, and specialized tours to make it easier for tourists to access food destinations and experiences.

4. Marketing and Promotion: Increase awareness of Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism offerings through targeted marketing campaigns that highlight the exclusive culinary heritage of the country. This can include social media marketing, website development, and participation in international food fairs and festivals.

5. Collaboration and Partnership: Encourage collaboration and partnership between government agencies, tourism boards, and local businesses to promote and develop gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan. This can help to identify areas for improvement and to develop new food-related experiences and attractions.

6. Specialized Tours: Develop and promote specialized food-related tours that showcase the rare culinary heritage of Uzbekistan, including cooking classes, food tastings, and visits to local markets and food producers.

6.CONCLUSION

In conclusion, gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan faces several challenges related to marketing, infrastructure, and service. These challenges include limited awareness of Uzbek cuisine among tourists, language barriers, limited accessibility to traditional food experiences, a lack of English proficiency among service staff, limited accommodation options, food safety and hygiene concerns, and a lack of specialized tours. Addressing these challenges is crucial to improving the overall experience for tourists and promoting sustainable, long-term growth in the tourism industry. To attract tourists, Uzbekistan can focus on showcasing its unique culinary heritage, offering a variety of food-related attractions and experiences, and developing infrastructure related to transportation, accommodation, and

specialized tours. By promoting its culinary offerings, Uzbekistan can attract visitors who are interested in experiencing the country's culture and traditions through its food. In comparison to Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan has a similar emphasis on traditional dishes, street food culture, and wine tourism. However, Azerbaijan has been more successful in recent years in promoting its cuisine through initiatives such as specialty restaurants, culinary festivals, and the Azerbaijan Cuisine Centre. Azerbaijan has also invested more heavily in developing its tourism infrastructure, with modern hotels, restaurants, and transportation options that cater to tourists. Finally, the infrastructure aspect of the industry requires development, particularly in transportation, accommodation, and specialized tours. The lack of specialized tours that focus specifically on gastronomic experiences in Uzbekistan is a significant challenge. By improving the quality of staff, food destinations, and marketing efforts, Uzbekistan can attract more visitors and establish itself as a leading gastronomic tourism destination.

REFERENCES:

Uzbekistan Tourism: <https://www.uzbekistan.travel/>

Azerbaijan Tourism Board: <https://azerbaijan.travel/>

Silk Road Food Tours: <https://www.silkroadfoodtours.com/>

Legislation: <https://lex.uz/uz/>

Food Tours in Uzbekistan: <https://www.visituzbekistan.travel/what-to-do/food-tours/>

Culinary Tours in Azerbaijan: <https://www.azerbaijan.travel/culinary-tours>

"The Georgian Feast: The Vibrant Culture and Savoury Food of the Republic of Georgia" by Darra Goldstein (<https://www.amazon.com/Georgian-Feast-Vibrant-Culture-Republic/dp/0520275916>)

"Uzbekistan: A Culinary Journey" by Caroline Eden

"Azerbaijan: Land of Fire and Flood - A Journey Through Food, Wine and Historical Azerbaijan" by Michael Kaminer

"The Role of Cuisine in Tourism" by Metin Kozak and Luisa Andreu

"Cultural Tourism in Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan: A Comparative Analysis" by ShahlaNaghiyeva

"Food and Drink Tourism: Principles and Practice" edited by Sally Everett and Donna Chambers

"The Caucasus: An Introduction" by Thomas de Waal